

SECTION B-B

SECTION A-A

DETAIL C
SCALE 2 : 1

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS			FINISH:		DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES		DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION	
SURFACE FINISH:							Gérard Zinzindhoué Project			
TOLERANCES:									TITLE:	
LINEAR:							UW-Camera_Front_2			
ANGULAR:							DWG NO.		A3	
DRAWN			NAME		SIGNATURE		DATE			
CHK'D										
APPV'D										
MFG										
Q.A							MATERIAL:		SCALE:1:1	
							WEIGHT:		SHEET 1 OF 1	